

The Rothman-Dahly Evidence Pyramid

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Evidence based medicine (EBM) is a movement aimed at integrating the best available scientific evidence with clinical expertise and patient preferences to support medical decision making (1). The concept of an *evidence hierarchy* has played a prominent role in EBM, and is often represented heuristically in the form of a pyramid (2), with “better” or more “useful” evidence placed towards the top. More specifically, evidence pyramids typically present randomized controlled trials (RCTs), and systematic reviews of RCTs, at the top of the pyramid. The message is that these studies generate more useful evidence than that generated by non-experimental study designs, also referred to as observational studies.

Heuristics are by definition shortcuts or simplifications intended as guidance for novices, and thus not well suited to provoke deeper, critical thinking on a topic. Consequently, evidence hierarchies and pyramids have been criticized for lacking important nuance. Among these critiques is a paper in which one of us (Rothman) argued that it is “mindless” to ascribe greater validity to one study design over another without any consideration of context (3). Dahly attempted to capture this idea in an even simpler evidence pyramid (figure 1), which he posted to twitter in 2017 with the caption “In case you were wondering, this is my evidence pyramid” (4). In 2018 Dahly returned to this tweet to acknowledge Rothman’s influence on his thinking (5).

Unfortunately a tweet is just a tweet, if can still be called that. Given the growing popularity of the *Rothman-Dahly Evidence Pyramid*, we have written this paper to serve as its canonical citation, and to make clear that the image has been dedicated to the public domain (CC0 1.0 Universal) (6), though citations to both this document and reference (3) below are always warmly appreciated.

Thoughtful, well-conducted studies of any design

Figure 1: The Rothman-Dahly Evidence Pyramid (original version)

Thoughtful, well-conducted studies of any design

Figure 2: The Rothman-Dahly Evidence Pyramid (sanitized version)

References

1. Sackett DL, Rosenberg WM, Gray JA, Haynes RB, Richardson WS. Evidence based medicine: what it is and what it isn't. *BMJ*. 1996 Jan 13;312(7023):71–2.
2. Blunt CJ. The Pyramid Schema: The Origins and Impact of Evidence Pyramids [Internet]. Rochester, NY: Social Science Research Network; 2022 [cited 2025 Dec 19]. Available from: <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=4297163>
3. Rothman KJ. Six persistent research misconceptions. *J Gen Intern Med*. 2014 July;29(7):1060–4.
4. Darren Dahly on Twitter: "In case you were wondering, this is MY evidence pyramid.... " [Internet]. 2021 [cited 2025 Dec 19]. Available from: <https://web.archive.org/web/20210616062210/https://twitter.com/statsepi/status/895012576714731520>
5. Darren Dahly on Twitter: "I was recently reminded by @PWGTennant that the motivation for this was certainly @ken_rothman's excellent essay on common misconceptions in science, which everyone should read. <https://t.co/MBHGT9GU62>... <https://t.co/bIJ11T9N0y>" [Internet]. 2021 [cited 2025 Dec 19]. Available from: <https://web.archive.org/web/20210616062208/https://twitter.com/statsepi/status/964812179156455424>
6. Deed - CC0 1.0 Universal - Creative Commons [Internet]. 2025 [cited 2025 Dec 19]. Available from: <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>